

WORK ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF A DIGITAL INFORMATION SYSTEM FOR THE TORATAU NATIONAL PARK

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Abstract

This article discusses the process and description of the work that was planned and carried out by a team of young scientists to develop an integrated digital information system for the Toratau Geopark. Existing scientific and practical knowledge about the geopark was analyzed and systematized. Methods of geospatial analysis were developed and adapted to collect and process data about the geopark. Field studies were conducted to verify data and refine parameters of models, and aerial photography was conducted on the territory of the geopark covering an area of approximately 80 hectares. A digital terrain model and digital model for the geopark were compiled.

Keywords: Geoparks; nature; society; sustainable development; biodiversity; education; resource conservation; socio-cultural aspects; economic contribution; environmental sustainability; excursions; harmony; cultural heritage; sustainable management; environmental education; regional development; interaction; geology; platform.

Geoparks are special areas where biological diversity and cultural heritage come together in a unique way, creating a symbiotic relationship. These places not only protect unique flora and fauna, but they also preserve a rich history and cultural traditions, which form the basis for environmental sustainability and harmony with nature [1, p. 149].

Geoparks were created to preserve natural and cultural treasures, and they serve as platforms for enhancing the interaction between society and the environment. The Toratau Geopark, located in the Republic of Bashkortostan, is an example of such a unique area that combines cultural heritage, geology, and biodiversity. Its preservation and promotion require the use of modern technology, such as the creation of a digital information system (Figure 1).

Figure 1 The geographical location of the Toratau Geopark on a map of the Republic of Bashkortostan.

In order to develop the Toratau Geopark, a spatial data infrastructure called "Geopark Web GIS Client Software Package" was created. This software package groups information into thematic information blocks, making it easier to access and understand.

To create a virtual reality representation of the area, a survey was conducted using unmanned aerial vehicles. The survey data allowed us to create a comprehensive three-dimensional model of the study area (Figure 2).

Figure 2 Mount Toratau and preparations for surveying the area with aerial photography.

Field work also includes an expedition study, during which an inventory of plant species will be made, and a complete list of honey plant species in the geopark will be created. Additionally, a soil survey of the geopark's territory will be conducted. A digital terrain model of the forest park and the geopark has been created. An in-depth analysis of geospatial data using geoinformation systems has been performed, allowing for the identification of key patterns and relationships within the geopark.

A multidisciplinary database containing information on the geopark's geological structure, biodiversity, historical and cultural sites, and other relevant data has been compiled. A comprehensive analysis of the geopark's geocological stability has been undertaken, focusing on its natural and territorial complex. At present, a group of young scientists are testing the functionality of the "Web GIS client" software package called "Geopark."

The software package provides users with an intuitive web interface, similar to those of modern geographic information systems. It has a wide range of applications, including education, scientific research, and ecotourism, for the virtual exploration of the geopark.

The main feature of the software is the ability to virtually travel through the geopark, creating routes for virtual exploration and presenting extensive information about geological, biological, and historical aspects of the territory. This is achieved through advanced web technologies, which allow users to visualize data in both digital and graphical formats. The information presented is highly detailed and interactive.

Such an integrated digital information system helps to attract more visitors and researchers, and increases awareness of the ecological and cultural significance of the geopark. It also contributes to the conservation of nature, cultural heritage, and the development of local communities and the economy.

This study proposes a new approach to integrating cultural heritage, geocology, and biodiversity through the use of modern technologies. This could be important for the sustainable development of Toratau Geopark and other similar territories.

References

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